

BIOTECHNOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF GENETICS.

Dadajanov Arafat Komiljanovich

PhD. dotsent.

Namangan of Textile industrial institute

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ABSTRACT

Today, the field of biotechnology is developing rapidly. With the development of biotechnology, we are learning more and more about the nature of genetics. Genes are biological material that is responsible for building all life on the planet. However, it should be noted that when the genetic nature changes synthetically, it leads to various mutational consequences. At the same time, various genetic diseases began to develop. With this approach, the human genetic fund deteriorates.

Based on the above, genetic research should be pure and natural. Biotechnology methods must meet all research criteria, but they must also be genetically pure. Our article covers all this.

Summary of the article:

Biologic aspect of genetics.

The article identifies the causes and ways of overcoming many of the problems mankind is facing today, no matter how economically developed the world is, the fundamentals and nature of development can be devastating and endless. It is no secret that such a situation is not known to the world, how many civilized civilizations in the past have disappeared from the earth because of their spiritual weakness. The development of society in the light of spiritual harmony is of great importance to the progress of religious sources and may contribute to modern science. It is important to study the religious sources and to contribute to the development of science. It contributes to the role of the spirit in self-regulation and self-control, and in the future to promote the principles of stability and mutual respect in public administration through clean and pure ideas in society.

Uzbekistan is rapidly developing in all directions, and the country has a large scientific base and scientific potential for this. Among this potential, there is mainly a great historical heritage and scientific figures like Ibn Sino (Avicenna), Aziziddin Nasafiy and other ancestors. They have left behind a great scientific potential for the benefit of all peoples of the world. Many of the technological and scientific solutions they left behind were simple and highly effective. In recent years, the President of Uzbekistan has opened a center for the study of Islamic civilization and a research institute for the study of Islam in Bukhara to study the heritage of Islamic figures in Central Asia. We all know that in Central Asia,

civilization and scientific progress are connected with the religion of Islam. During this period, psychology, medicine, astronomy, mathematics, geography, biotechnology and philosophy successfully developed in Central Asia. In the field of biotechnology, the great scientist Avicenna made a great breakthrough. Avicenna was the first to introduce biotechnology into medicine.

For example:

The story of Avicenna says that during that period one of the sons of the Emir from Central Asia fell ill. Avicenna prescribed pork medicine for healing. The Emir strictly refused this medicine for religious reasons. Then Avicenna prepared a biotechnological mixture of pork, covered it with earth, and poured the seeds of rapidly maturing greens over it. Thus, he produced a biotechnologically edible, religiously motivated pork medicine. From this, it can be concluded that our ancestors, like Avicenna, knew biotechnological methods of preparing various biologically useful technologies for growing and manufacturing medicines and used these technologies.

Today, various diseases and their types appear. Various medicines are offered for their treatment, which are ineffective today.

The human immune system decreases daily and, therefore, the need for effective medicines increases. The treatment approach to many diseases is to raise the immune system. With a rapid increase in immunity, many chronic and complex virological diseases can be cured with medicines. In this regard, in many diseases, the surgical method of raising immunity is the main means of rapid recovery.

Several factors affect the decrease in human immunity, for example:

Environmental degradation:

1. An increase in many harmful elements in the water
2. Reduction of useful elements in agricultural products, increase in nitrates and chemicals.
3. Air pollution

Sedentary life also acts to reduce immunity.

All these factors act on human genes and cause the occurrence of infectious and genetic diseases.

From this, it can be concluded that these factors not only affect changes in physiology but also changes in human genetic forms. Each human gene is a brick of the foundation for building a body. Changes in one brick in the foundation of the human gene lead to the appearance of a large change in the human body. If environmental and life factors lead to genetic changes, then using these factors can influence the opposite-as beneficial factors of action on genetic changes.

Human evolves in stages from a low genetic form to a high one. Human stands at the very pinnacle of evolution as he evolved from a simple genetic form to a plant form and then passed on to an animal. Viruses that cause diseases have also undergone this evolution.

Human genes consist of various codes that respond to future physiological and genetic conditions. The codes consist of active and inactive ones. The active codes are those that match the codes of the genes of the pair. The mismatched codes are not destroyed, but wait for their turn in the next generation. There are also codes that have a positive and non-positive effect on a person.

When a human's immunity drops, non-positively influencing codes increase their effects on the body. Then the preserved viruses cause various diseases in the body. On the contrary, an increase in immunity weakens these viruses and the disease itself reduces or destroys its function of action. Therefore, in some cases, even if life is satisfactory and satisfying, with a weakening of the immune system, various phenomena of the disease appear in the body. For example, in your family, someone was ill with a serious illness, with a decline in immunity, this disease can manifest its activity in your body.

This means that all people have the same codes, but their effect on the body is different. This means that the codes operate in different ways. The possibility of matching the variant is different for everyone and acts according to the degree of immunity.

The codes of the plant and animal worlds differ from each other, and they also differ from the human world together. Human codes are much larger than plant and animal codes. The plant world has fewer codes than an animal, and animals are much smaller than humans. When all plant and animal codes are working, everything is exactly inferior to human in quantity.

The codes are activated already in the womb, but the codes that are not involved can be activated during life. Some codes are involved in changes in immunity, but in some cases, in most cases, in stressful situations.

With a drop in immunity, in some situations, diseases are not cured by medicines prepared from plants and animals, even if they have complex cooking options. This means that the molecular composition of viruses causing diseases is higher than the molecular structure of animals and plants. To cure high-molecular-weight viral diseases, we need to have equal or increased funds. To do this, we use the most sophisticated highly coded means to obtain finished products.

In some cases, even highly coded means do not work, in which case a person's vital signs stop, genes stop their function.

We have been studying religious sources, sources of great thinkers for many years and decided that in the field of biotechnology and medicine, fertilizers and medicinal substances that contribute to improving the soil of the earth and human health can be obtained using simple methods of biotechnology.

The scientist, associate professor of Chemical Sciences (Dadazhanov Komilzhonohun Dadazhonovich) said:

"If the soil is good, fertile, it doesn't matter what kind of produce you received, it will still be useful. If the soil is infertile, the plant will take everything from the soil to fertilize its fruit, everything bad and harmful. In the end, we will get harmful products for health. This is nature and it teaches us, not us. The laws of nature are the laws of God and we cannot change them. But we can use them with good intentions".

From the above, we have selected several of the plant and animal elements that affect the human body very quickly,[3].[4].[5].:

Vegetable: 1. Fir trees 2. Cotton 3. Sandy-bushy (yantak - saxaul, yulgun - grebenshchik (tamarix)) 4. Cereals (millet, corn)

Animals: 1. The cow 2. Sheep 3. The Rabbit 4. The Goat

All elements are selected as biotechnological elements.

Of all the elements, the fastest-acting parts are separated, and a biotechnological

mixture is prepared. The mixture is enriched with poultry egg. The enriched mixture is used as fertilizers - this is the first stage of obtaining a biotechnological enriched product. The whole technology of obtaining a biotechnological product consists of five stages.

The finished product can be prepared anywhere and under any conditions. The final product consists of different products and in different forms of vegetables, fruits, meat, water, etc., etc.

The product is mainly used as a medicine to boost the immune system. In many diseases, medicines do not work to cure them. Medicine in such cases tries to raise the human immune system at least a little. In addition, many diseases appear due to a decrease in immunity. These diseases are such as AIDS, oncological diseases, various virological diseases.

We believe that many diseases from ancient times take place and hide in our body. Nevertheless, with a drop in immunity, diseases come out. They break down the protective wall of the body, once in the blood, gradually destroy the body. It is useless to treat such diseases with conventional medicines. The biotechnological products we offer are very useful, harmless and have medicinal properties.

According to our research on the genetic aspects of biotechnology, it should be noted that some bio elements act on the human body very quickly and affect the body in such a way that chronic diseases such as bronchial asthma, tuberculosis, jaundice, heart diseases, and skin diseases appear in the body. It follows from this that bio elements of plant and animal organisms affect the human body genetically. What does it mean that some bio elements produce mutational changes in the human body? According to our research, it follows that if bio elements mutate (change) human cells, then they can be used as antimutation elements. They can be used as elements that enhance human immunity.

Environmental, physico-biological and vital aspects affect human immunity.

When the environment deteriorates, water, air and soil deteriorate.

In physico-biological aspects, as the deviation of the earth from its axis. In this case, many plants change their ability to act on the body and their healing properties decrease.

In life aspects, sedentary life, poor nutrition and genetically modified foods.

Many virological diseases increase a person's body temperature. They cause nausea, vomiting, and the appearance of mucus in the mouth, eyes and nose, joint pain. These symptoms appear in almost all viral diseases. Of course, different diseases differ in other symptoms, but the above symptoms are detected in almost all diseases.

Viruses are very ancient, very tenacious - highly molecular compounds. Their rate of action decreases at low temperatures, but they are not destroyed. They are destroyed by very high temperatures. They spread rapidly in dark, colorless places. Their favorite place is uncleansed, dirty places. For example, under the claws, under the hair, under the armpit and in other secluded places of our body. All these signs remind us of highly developed beings, as invisible to our eyes, but living organisms. Viruses are alive, very smart and harmful to us. They have entered our body and suddenly appear, destroying our body. Where did they come from in our body? Why are they waiting for our body to weaken? They act very quickly and deftly. They destroy our living cells in the shortest possible time. Did God make us so fragile? Human nature consists of sand, water, air and fire, and has also endowed us with a soul. But there is nothing untold about viruses. But God told man that by creating him, he

exalted him before other beings. But God said that man would weaken and become the lowest being if he renounced him. A person will also weaken when God wants to in old age, at the end of life. This means that our immunity decreases with old age and from an immoral life. However, how did this virus get into our body? If it was not in nature. Again, we will have to face the ancient history of man. As we know from religious sources, Adam and Eve were at enmity with Satan. Satan really wanted to harm a person. In order to control and inhabit a human, he wanted to mix his blood with human blood. Knowing the nature of man, he came up with a way to anger a person. Satan left his son to Eve in the form of a lamb and asked her to look after him. Upon learning that the lamb was the son of Satan, Adam became angry and bit into the lamb's neck, aiming to kill it. When bitten, the blood of the child of Satan fell into the Human mouth, and thus a very ancient, harmful and highly developed structure entered our body. Until then, it hides in our body. It always reminds us of itself when our body weakens.

In some cases, the body cannot digest food and medicine with the help of the stomach. Also with the help of organs, such as the liver, kidneys and our other assimilating organs. In such cases, we propose a human organ like the navel to raise immunity. As we know, a person in the womb assimilated everything through his navel. Our proposed biological products can be used in the above way. Biological elements are designed so that they absorb the disease through the navel and transfer the necessary elements into the human body. Thus, it is possible to increase human immunity in the shortest possible time. After such a session, other methods can be used to improve the patient's health.

Conclusions

1. Harmless biotechnology it is based on pure ideology. Biotechnological methods must be combined with nature.
2. Genetic research can be introduced using pure biotechnology.
3. Genetic change manifesting natural and vital aspects can also be changed by the opposite of the aspects themselves.
4. A person should create biological methods of healing from various diseases; they should be clean, simple and accessible.

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